

Theobromine and Parkinson's disease

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Abstract

The defining neuropathological features of Parkinson's disease (PD) include the progressive loss of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra, together with the intraneuronal accumulation of α -synuclein in the form of Lewy bodies. Theobromine has been shown to possess neuroprotective effects, preventing neuronal damage, enhancing motor memory and cognitive function in humans (Gao et al. 2022). Bhat et al. (2021) demonstrated the neuroprotective effects of theobromine in a rat model of transient global cerebral ischemia/reperfusion (tGCI/R). The study of Haj Ahmed et al. (2020) investigated the interaction between several methylxanthines and primary amine oxidase (PrAO)/ monoamine oxidase (MAO) in human subcutaneous adipose tissue (hScAT). Caffeine and theobromine produced a remarkable 50% inhibition of PrAO activity when incubated at 2.5 mM with hScAT. Due to its low side-effect profile and minimal toxicity at appropriate doses, theobromine and its derivatives are considered promising agents for the prevention of neurological disorders, offering potential applications in medicine.

Keywords

MAO-A/B inhibition, Parkinson's disease, theobromine

Neurodegeneration and neurodegenerative diseases

Neurons are fundamental to the proper functioning of the human brain, serving as the primary units of communication within neural networks. While most neurons are generated within the brain, they are also distributed throughout the body. During early development, neural stem cells give rise to the majority of neurons, although their numbers decline substantially in adulthood. Although neurons are not permanent, their progressive loss—whether in number, structure, or function—defines neurodegeneration, a process central to the pathophysiology of numerous brain disorders and a significant public health concern. Neurodegeneration is characterized by synaptic dysfunction, disruption of neural circuits, and

accumulation of aberrantly modified proteins within the brain. Disorders in which neurodegeneration is the defining pathological feature are collectively classified as neurodegenerative diseases (NDs) (Lamprey et al. 2022).

Neurodegeneration describes the gradual loss of neurons, marked by ongoing neuronal cell death that results in cognitive and motor impairments, depending on which brain regions are affected. The brain is particularly vulnerable to age-related changes, which contribute to neurodegenerative processes and the development of various neurodegenerative disorders (Peña-Bautista et al. 2020). In its strict definition, neurodegeneration refers to pathological processes that predominantly target neurons. Clinically, neurodegenerative diseases comprise a broad and diverse group of neurological disorders characterized by heterogeneous clinical presentations

and pathological features, selectively involving particular neuronal populations within defined functional and anatomical systems. These conditions are typically of unknown etiology and exhibit a progressive and irreversible course (Przedborski et al. 2003).

Oxidative stress represents a key pathological feature of multiple diseases, including dementia and other neurodegenerative disorders. Among reactive oxygen species (ROS), hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) is frequently regarded as a central mediator of redox-regulated processes that become dysregulated in neurodegenerative conditions (Konno et al. 2021).

The generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) via the catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide by ferrous ion is referred to as the Fenton reaction (Chen 2019).

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) can be broadly classified into two categories: low-reactivity species, such as superoxide anion ($\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$) and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), and highly reactive species, including hydroxyl radicals and peroxynitrites, which are generated through Fenton and Haber–Weiss reactions involving H_2O_2 . While low-reactivity ROS function in physiological signaling as secondary messengers, highly reactive ROS are primarily responsible for oxidative damage and subsequent cell death. Forster et al. demonstrated that oxidative stress is associated with cognitive decline in rodent models, whereas neuronal loss contributes to brain aging and may initiate the development of neurodegenerative diseases (Lee et al. 2021).

Neurodegenerative disorders may be broadly categorized according to their predominant clinical manifestations, most commonly including extrapyramidal and pyramidal movement abnormalities as well as cognitive and behavioral impairments. Pure clinical syndromes are relatively rare, as the majority of patients exhibit overlapping or mixed symptomatology. At present, definitive diagnosis relies on neuropathological assessment performed post mortem. While neurodegenerative diseases are often distinguished by disease-specific protein aggregates and selective regional vulnerability, they share a number of core pathogenic mechanisms underlying progressive neuronal dysfunction and loss. These include proteostasis disruption with associated impairments in the ubiquitin–proteasome and autophagy–lysosome pathways, oxidative stress, regulated cell death pathways, and chronic neuroinflammatory responses (Dugger et al. 2017).

Degeneration of the central nervous system (CNS) is defined by a chronic and progressive deterioration of neuronal structure and function, ultimately leading to cognitive, functional, and behavioral deficits. Although the underlying mechanisms driving neuronal degeneration are not yet fully elucidated, the prevalence of neurodegenerative processes increases with advancing age, particularly during middle to late adulthood. Neurodegeneration predominantly affects older populations and is a hallmark

of disorders such as Alzheimer's disease (AD), Parkinson's disease (PD), multiple sclerosis (MS), and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), including cases associated with viral infections. Viruses can contribute to neuronal damage either through direct cytotoxic effects or by triggering apoptotic pathways, thereby promoting neurodegenerative processes. In multiple sclerosis, characteristic pathological changes include disruption of blood–brain barrier (BBB) integrity, demyelination, axonal injury, glial scar formation, and infiltration of inflammatory cells—primarily lymphocytes—into the CNS. The resultant loss of myelin underlies the clinical manifestations of the disease, which encompass neuropathic pain, paralysis, muscle spasticity, and optic neuritis (Chen et al. 2016).

The most prevalent NDs include Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, prion disorders, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, motor neuron diseases, Huntington's disease, spinal muscular atrophy, and spinocerebellar ataxias (Lamprey et al. 2022).

Parkinson's disease (PD)

Parkinson's disease (PD), also referred to as idiopathic or primary parkinsonism, hypokinetic–rigid syndrome, or paralysis agitans, represents the second most prevalent progressive neurodegenerative disorder, affecting approximately 2–3% of individuals over the age of 65. Epidemiological data indicate that Parkinson's disease affects at least 1% of the population aged over 60 years and represents the most rapidly increasing neurodegenerative disorder on a global scale. The majority of cases are sporadic in nature; however, roughly 10% are attributed to genetic factors, with approximately 3–5% of patients harboring inherited pathogenic variants in established PD-associated genes (Zafar et al. 2025).

The defining neuropathological features of PD include the progressive loss of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra, together with the intraneuronal accumulation of α -synuclein in the form of Lewy bodies. Parkinson's disease is a progressive neurodegenerative condition in which the central pathological feature is the accumulation of aggregated α -synuclein. Evidence derived from cellular and animal models, biochemical investigations, and analyses of neurons from patients with PD demonstrates aberrant α -synuclein deposition within the enteric nervous system, particularly the myenteric plexus, followed by the propagation of pathology between the gastrointestinal tract, brainstem, olfactory system, and additional brain regions. These processes are thought to contribute to both the onset and progression of the disease. At the cellular and subcellular levels, impairments in lysosomal, endosomal, and mitochondrial function have been consistently identified. Moreover, recent findings suggest that dysregulated immune and inflammatory responses originating in the gut play a contributory role in the overall pathogenesis of PD (Zafar et al. 2025).

The regional accumulation of α -synuclein within the brain, most notably in the substantia nigra, results in progressive neuronal degeneration and a subsequent reduction of dopaminergic signaling within the basal ganglia, which are critical for the regulation of motor control and muscle tone. Deposition of α -synuclein in the gastrointestinal tract and other peripheral sites also provides a mechanistic explanation for the frequent occurrence of non-motor symptoms in PD, such as impaired gastrointestinal motility with constipation and rapid eye movement sleep behavior disorder, which often precede the appearance of classical motor symptoms by several years. Consequently, advancing insights into PD etiology indicate that the disorder cannot be adequately explained solely by dopaminergic neuron loss in the substantia nigra. Rather, PD involves a multifaceted and widespread pathophysiological process, with the non-genetic drivers of α -synuclein aggregation in the brain remaining an active area of investigation (Zafar et al. 2025).

Historically, Parkinson's disease (PD) was primarily attributed to the progressive degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the *substantia nigra*, which was considered responsible for the hallmark motor symptoms. However, recent clinical and neuropathological evidence indicates that this represents only a partial view of the disease. Currently, PD is conceptualized in three stages: (1) the pre-clinical phase, in which neurodegeneration has begun but no symptoms are apparent; (2) the prodromal phase, during which neurodegenerative changes in both the central and peripheral nervous systems lead to observable, though non-motor or subtle, clinical features; and (3) the clinical phase, characterized by overt motor symptoms sufficient for diagnosis. Consequently, initial signs of PD may emerge well before the classic motor manifestations and without significant dopaminergic neuronal loss in the brain (Pardo-Moreno et al. 2023).

Parkinson's disease is clinically defined by four core motor manifestations, commonly summarized by the acronym TRAP: resting tremor, rigidity, akinesia or bradykinesia, and postural instability. Additional hallmark features of parkinsonism include a stooped posture and episodic freezing of movement, with PD representing the most prevalent parkinsonian syndrome. Given the heterogeneity in clinical presentation, daily activities, and personal circumstances of individuals with PD, both motor and non-motor deficits should be assessed in relation to each patient's specific functional requirements and therapeutic objectives (Jankovic 2008).

Bradykinesia, defined as slowness of movement, represents the most characteristic clinical manifestation of Parkinson's disease, although it may also occur in other conditions. As a key feature of basal ganglia dysfunction, it involves impaired planning, initiation, and execution of movements, particularly during sequential or simultaneous motor tasks. Clinically, bradykinesia initially presents as reduced speed in activities of daily living and delayed reaction times, often affecting fine motor skills. Additional features include diminished spontaneous movements and

gestures, hypophonic and monotonic speech, hypomimia with reduced blinking, drooling due to impaired swallowing, and decreased arm swing during gait. Because of its recognisable nature, bradykinesia may be evident prior to formal neurological assessment and is typically evaluated using rapid, repetitive motor tasks with attention to movement speed and amplitude decrement (Jankovic 2008).

Bradykinesia is modulated by emotional state, as illustrated by *kinesia paradoxa*, whereby patients may transiently perform rapid movements in response to strong external stimuli, suggesting preserved motor programs that are difficult to access without external cues. Although its precise pathophysiology remains incompletely understood, bradykinesia shows the strongest correlation with dopaminergic deficiency among PD symptoms. Neuroimaging studies demonstrate that reduced striatal dopaminergic activity parallels the severity of bradykinesia, supporting the hypothesis that impaired dopamine-mediated modulation of cortical-subcortical motor networks underlies this phenomenon. Dysfunction within the putamen and globus pallidus leads to insufficient muscle activation and force generation, resulting in reduced movement velocity and amplitude (Jankovic 2008).

Rest tremor is the most frequent and readily identifiable motor symptom of Parkinson's disease. It typically presents unilaterally, with a frequency of 4–6 Hz, and predominantly affects the distal portions of the limbs. In the hands, it classically manifests as a supination-pronation “pill-rolling” movement that may later become bilateral. Rest tremor may also involve the lips, chin, jaw, and legs; however, unlike essential tremor, involvement of the head, neck, or voice is uncommon, making head tremor more suggestive of essential tremor or cervical dystonia rather than PD. Characteristically, rest tremor diminishes during voluntary movement and disappears during sleep, and some patients report a subjective sensation of internal tremor without visible oscillations (Jankovic 2008).

Many individuals with PD also exhibit postural tremor, which in some cases may be more disabling than rest tremor and represent the initial clinical manifestation. Parkinsonian postural tremor, often termed re-emergent tremor, is distinguished from essential tremor by a latency period following arm extension and by its shared frequency with rest tremor, as well as its responsiveness to dopaminergic therapy, suggesting a common underlying mechanism. Nonetheless, essential tremor may coexist with PD, with distinguishing features including a long-standing history of action tremor, positive family history, head or voice involvement, absence of latency on arm extension, tremor improvement with alcohol or β -blockers, and characteristic handwriting changes. Accumulating evidence further supports essential tremor as a potential risk factor for the subsequent development of PD (Jankovic 2008).

The presence and severity of rest tremor vary among patients and across disease stages. While the majority of individuals with PD develop tremor at some point during the disease course, a minority may exhibit minimal or absent tremor clinically. Neuropathological studies indicate

that prominent tremor in PD is associated with degeneration of specific midbrain neuronal populations, particularly within the A8 region, which appears relatively preserved in patients without tremor (Jankovic 2008).

Rigidity in Parkinson's disease is defined by increased resistance to passive limb movements, often accompanied by the "cogwheel" phenomenon, especially when tremor is present. It can affect both proximal regions, such as the neck, shoulders, and hips, and distal regions, including the wrists and ankles. Reinforcing manoeuvres, such as voluntary movements of the contralateral limb (Froment's manoeuvre), can accentuate rigidity and help detect mild cases.

Rigidity may be painful, with shoulder discomfort frequently representing an early PD symptom, though it is often misattributed to arthritis, bursitis, or rotator cuff injury. In a prospective study of 6,038 individuals (mean age 68.5) without baseline parkinsonism or dementia, stiffness, tremor, and imbalance were all associated with a higher risk of developing PD (hazard ratios 2.11, 2.09, and 3.47, respectively). Over an average follow-up of 5.8 years, 56 participants were diagnosed with PD (Jankovic 2008).

Postural instability, resulting from impaired postural reflexes, typically emerges in the later stages of Parkinson's disease, following the onset of other motor symptoms. The pull test, in which a patient is briskly pulled backward or forward, assesses retropulsion or propulsion; taking more than two steps backward or failing to respond indicates abnormal postural reflexes. Along with freezing of gait, postural instability is a leading cause of falls and contributes substantially to the risk of hip fractures. The delayed onset of falls in PD distinguishes it from other neurodegenerative disorders such as progressive supranuclear palsy (PSP) and multiple system atrophy (MSA), with mean times to first fall reported at 108 months in PD versus 16.8 and 42 months in PSP and MSA, respectively.

The occurrence of postural instability is influenced by multiple factors, including other parkinsonian symptoms, orthostatic hypotension, age-related sensory decline, and impaired integration of visual, vestibular, and proprioceptive input. Fear of falling further compromises balance. In one study, 38% of patients experienced falls, with 13% falling more than once weekly, and fall frequency correlated with disease severity. While dopaminergic therapy, pallidotomy, and deep brain stimulation can improve some axial symptoms, postural instability generally remains resistant to treatment. Emerging approaches, including targeting the zona incerta and pedunculopontine nucleus in addition to the subthalamic nucleus and globus pallidus, are being investigated to address gait and balance deficits (Jankovic 2008).

Currently, Parkinson's disease (PD) has no curative or disease-modifying therapies, and treatment is primarily aimed at alleviating motor and non-motor symptoms. Pharmacological management focuses on restoring dopaminergic function, with Levodopa considered the mainstay therapy. However, its use is limited by adverse effects, particularly dyskinesia, and by reduced responsiveness as the disease advances, necessitating higher and more

frequent doses. To enhance bioavailability and limit peripheral metabolism, Levodopa is co-administered with decarboxylase inhibitors, such as Carbidopa or Benserazide. Combination therapy is often employed to mitigate complications associated with high doses of a single agent, including the addition of monoamine oxidase B (MAOB) inhibitors (rasagiline, safinamide, selegiline) and catechol-O-methyltransferase (COMT) inhibitors (entacapone, tolcapone). These adjuncts improve dopamine levels, stabilize fluctuations, and enhance Levodopa absorption, particularly at the gastrointestinal level where COMT activity is prominent (Pardo-Moreno et al. 2023).

Another class of medications includes dopamine agonists, such as ropinirole and pramipexole, which have demonstrated safety and efficacy both as monotherapy and in combination with Levodopa. Notable agents within this group include rotigotine, available as transdermal patches that allow continuous drug delivery, and apomorphine, which serves as a rescue therapy for motor fluctuations and is administered via injections or subcutaneous infusion (Pardo-Moreno et al. 2023).

Cognitive impairment, depression, sleep disturbances, and autonomic dysfunction are among the most prevalent non-motor manifestations of Parkinson's disease. Cognitive deficits are commonly managed with acetylcholinesterase inhibitors, including Donepezil, Galantamine, and Rivastigmine. Depression in PD patients is frequently treated with serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs), such as Duloxetine, Desvenlafaxine, Milnacipran, and Venlafaxine. Additional therapeutic options include benzodiazepines (e.g., Alprazolam, Clonazepam, Diazepam, Lorazepam), selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) such as Fluoxetine and Sertraline, tricyclic antidepressants (e.g., Amitriptyline, Imipramine, Nortriptyline), and other anxiolytics including Buspirone, Propranolol, Quetiapine, and Trazodone. Sleep disorders are often addressed using medications such as Amitriptyline, Clonazepam, Doxepin, Eszopiclone, Melatonin, Mirtazapine, and Trazodone (Pardo-Moreno et al. 2023).

Methylxanthines – structure and effects

Methylxanthines are plant-derived compounds present in significant amounts in tea, coffee, and chocolate. The most studied members of this group—theophylline, theobromine, and caffeine—are commonly recognized as mild central nervous system stimulants (Haj Ahmed et al. 2020).

Methylxanthines are heterocyclic organic compounds derived from xanthine through methylation, comprising fused pyrimidinedione and imidazole rings. The most commonly encountered naturally occurring methylxanthines include caffeine (1,3,7-trimethylxanthine), theophylline (1,3-dimethylxanthine), and theobromine (3,7-dimethylxanthine), which differ in both the number and position of N-methyl groups—caffeine having three,

while theophylline and theobromine have two. Paraxanthine (1,7-dimethylxanthine) is another relevant methylxanthine, but unlike the others, it is not produced by plants and instead arises as a human metabolite of caffeine (Monteiro et al. 2019) (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Chemical structures of natural methylxanthines.

Methylxanthines are widely distributed across the Plant Kingdom, being found in nearly 100 species spanning 13 plant orders, including tea (*Camellia sinensis* L.), coffee (*Coffea* spp.), and cacao (*Theobroma cacao* L.). Caffeine content in *Coffea* species ranges from 0.4% to 2.4% of dry weight, while *Camellia sinensis*, *Camellia assamica*, and *Camellia taliensis* contain 2–3% caffeine. Theobromine is present in some *Camellia* species, but *Theobroma cacao* is generally recognized as its primary natural source (Monteiro et al. 2019).

Theobromine, historically known as xantheose, is a naturally occurring bitter alkaloid belonging to the purine-based heterocyclic methylxanthines, formed through the methylation of xanthine. While methylxanthines such as theobromine, caffeine, and theophylline share similar chemical structures, they differ in their physiological effects. Theobromine is primarily found in the seeds of the cocoa tree, which grows in tropical regions of South America, where cocoa beans contain approximately 3.3% of this compound. Other dietary sources include kola nut, guarana, tea, and yaupon holly (Zhang et al. 2024).

Caffeine, chemically 1,3,7-trimethylxanthine, is another central nervous system stimulant closely related to theobromine. With an additional methyl group compared to theobromine (3,7-dimethylxanthine), caffeine crosses the blood–brain barrier more efficiently, producing stronger CNS stimulation. In contrast, theobromine has a longer half-life and milder side effects, acting as a gentle stimulant without the dependency issues commonly associated with caffeine. During caffeine metabolism, roughly

15% of its methyl groups are converted into theobromine. Theophylline, another related methylxanthine, primarily functions as a bronchodilator by relaxing airway smooth muscle and is used in the treatment of bronchial asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (Zhang et al. 2024). Table 1 shows a comparison of properties and functions of methylxanthines and adenosine.

Traditionally, four primary mechanisms have been proposed to explain the physiological effects of methylxanthines: antagonism of adenosine receptors, inhibition of phosphodiesterases, modulation of receptor activity, and regulation of intracellular calcium levels via ryanodine channels. Among these, adenosine receptor antagonism is considered the principal mechanism, predominantly targeting A1 and A2A receptors, with inhibitory activity typically observed in the millimolar concentration range (Monteiro et al. 2019). Through their pleiotropic actions on multiple pathways implicated in neurodegenerative disorders, and given their relatively mild side-effect profile, methylxanthines have been proposed as a promising strategy for the management of neurodegeneration (Janitschke et al. 2021).

Theobromine acts as a non-selective antagonist of adenosine receptors, thereby modulating intracellular levels of the second messenger cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP). Adenosine receptors, which belong to the G protein-coupled receptor family, include subtypes A1, A2A, A2B, and A3, each characterized by seven transmembrane α -helices. By coupling with G proteins, these receptors transmit extracellular signals into intracellular responses, primarily through cAMP-dependent pathways and the cAMP/protein kinase A (PKA) signaling cascade. Activation of A1 and A3 receptors decreases cAMP levels via G_i proteins, whereas stimulation of A2A and A2B receptors increases cAMP levels through G_s-mediated mechanisms (Zhang et al. 2024).

A1, A2B, and A3 adenosine receptors are highly abundant and widely distributed throughout the central nervous system (CNS), whereas A2A receptors are mainly found in peripheral tissues such as the heart and blood vessels, with a more restricted CNS presence, particularly in the striatum and posterior brain regions. Exogenous ligands targeting these receptors can modulate adenylate

Table 1. Comparison of properties and functions of methylxanthines and adenosine.

	Theobromine	Caffeine	Theophylline	Adenosine
Mode of action	Mild central nervous system stimulation	Central nervous system stimulation	Bronchodilation, cardiac stimulation	Neurotransmitter, inhibitory effect
Solubility in water	1 g/L	20 g/L	5 g/L	6.67 g/L
Toxicological nature	Generally considered safe in moderate amounts	Generally considered safe in moderate amounts	Can be toxic in high doses, narrow therapeutic range	Generally considered safe in moderate amounts
In vitro/In vivo experiments	Various studies suggest antioxidant properties, smooth muscle relaxation, and mild diuretic effects	Extensively studied for its effects on alertness, cognitive function, and metabolism	Bronchodilation effects demonstrated in vitro and in vivo	Modulation of neurotransmission, studied in various neurological disorders
LD50	1 g/Kg	0.12–0.2 g/Kg	blood concentration > 20 μ g/ml	
Elimination half-life	6–8 h	3–7 h	5–8 h	< 10 s

cyclase activity, either enhancing or inhibiting it depending on the cell type. Adenosine receptor signaling has been implicated in the pathogenesis of conditions including type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and neurological disorders, highlighting its potential as a therapeutic target (Zhang et al. 2024).

The metabolic pathways of theobromine (TB) in humans have been extensively characterized. TB is primarily metabolized via cytochrome P450 (CYP)-mediated N3- and N7-demethylation, yielding 7-methylxanthine (7-MX) and 3-methylxanthine (3-MX), respectively. Subsequently, 7-MX undergoes further oxidation by xanthine oxidase to form the corresponding monomethylurate, 7-methyluric acid. The formation of 7-MX and 3-MX accounts for approximately 60% and 20% of theobromine clearance, respectively. The remaining fraction of TB elimination involves its conversion to 3,7-dimethyluric acid (3,7-DMU), 6-amino-5-[N-methylformylamino]-1-methyluracil (3,7-DAU; a diaminouracil derivative), as well as renal excretion of the unmetabolized compound (Gates et al. 1999) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Theobromine metabolism pathways in humans.

The earliest evidence suggesting a potential neuroprotective effect of caffeine originates from the Honolulu Heart Program, a large-scale prospective study involving 8004 Japanese-American men followed over a 30-year period. The findings indicate that a daily intake of ≥ 784 mg/kg of coffee during midlife was associated with an approximately fivefold reduction in the risk of developing Parkinson's disease by the age of 65, compared to non-coffee consumers, after adjustment for age and smoking (Ross et

al. 2000). This inverse association between caffeine intake and the risk of developing Parkinson's disease was further corroborated by findings from the Health Professionals' Follow-Up Study and the Nurses' Health Study, which included 47,351 men and 88,565 women, respectively. Additional support has been provided by several other large prospective investigations, including the Finnish Mobile Clinic Health Examination Survey (Saaksjarvi et al. 2008), the NeuroGenetics Research Consortium (Powers et al. 2008), and a Danish case-control study focusing on idiopathic Parkinson's disease (Kyrozis et al. 2013).

Several mechanisms have been proposed to explain the neuroprotective effects of caffeine, including the regulation of glutamatergic excitotoxicity and neuroinflammatory processes mediated through adenosine receptor signaling (Chen et al. 2013). In addition, recent advances in understanding the roles of autophagy and the gut microbiota in Parkinson's disease pathogenesis suggest that caffeine may influence disease development by modulating autophagic pathways—potentially via its metabolic effects—as well as by directly altering the composition and function of the gut microbiome (Ren et al. 2020).

Evidence from epidemiological studies supporting the neuroprotective effects of caffeine is reinforced by a growing body of experimental data from animal models. These studies demonstrate that caffeine exerts protective effects against dopaminergic neurodegeneration in neurotoxin-based models of Parkinson's disease employing mitochondrial toxins such as MPTP, 6-OHDA, and rotenone (Chen et al. 2001; Ikeda et al. 2002; Xu et al. 2002; Aguiar et al. 2006), as well as in α -synuclein transmission models involving intracerebral injection of α -synuclein fibrils (Luan et al. 2018).

Both acute and chronic administration of caffeine have been shown to mitigate MPTP-induced dopaminergic neurotoxicity and neuronal loss (Chen et al. 2001; Xu et al. 2002). Notably, in a chronic MPTP infusion model, caffeine retained its neuroprotective properties even when administered after the initiation of the neurodegenerative process (i.e., 14 days following MPTP exposure) (Sonsalla et al. 2012).

Moreover, Luan et al. (2018) reported that caffeine attenuates pathological alterations induced by the A53T mutant form of α -synuclein in vivo using an α -synuclein fibril-based model of Parkinson's disease, an effect that was associated with enhanced autophagic activity, particularly macroautophagy and chaperone-mediated autophagy.

Notably, effects comparable to those of caffeine have been observed following pharmacological inhibition or genetic ablation of the adenosine A2A receptor (A2AR) - the principal central nervous system target of caffeine - both of which confer protection against dopaminergic neurodegeneration in experimental models of Parkinson's disease (Chen et al. 2001; Ikeda et al. 2002; Kachroo and Schwarzschild 2012). These findings suggest that the neuroprotective actions of caffeine are largely mediated through A2AR signaling pathways.

In addition, emerging evidence indicates that A2AR modulates α -synuclein aggregation and associated

cytotoxicity in SH-SY5Y cells (Ferreira et al. 2017a), while A2AR antagonism ameliorates synaptic dysfunction and cognitive impairments in α -synuclein transgenic mouse models of Parkinson's disease (Ferreira et al. 2017b). Collectively, these studies provide a mechanistic framework supporting the inverse association between caffeine consumption and Parkinson's disease risk, and highlight the therapeutic potential of caffeine and A2AR antagonists as disease-modifying strategies.

Caffeine has consistently been demonstrated to exert neuroprotective effects across a range of Parkinson's disease models, including those based on neurotoxins (e.g., MPTP, 6-OHDA, and rotenone) as well as α -synuclein-driven models. However, in contrast to these findings, caffeine has been reported to potentiate neurotoxicity induced by methamphetamine. Further investigation is therefore required to elucidate the context-dependent nature of caffeine's effects on neurotoxicity (Ren et al. 2020).

Theobromine functions as a competitive, non-selective inhibitor of phosphodiesterases (PDEs), interfering with the hydrolysis of intracellular second messengers, cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) and cyclic guanosine monophosphate (cGMP), thereby increasing intracellular cAMP levels (Zhang et al. 2024). Cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) activates the cAMP response element-binding protein (CREB), a transcription factor implicated in numerous neural processes, including the regulation of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) expression. BDNF is essential for neuronal survival and supports key functions such as learning and memory. Accordingly, the cAMP/CREB/BDNF signaling axis plays a critical role in cognitive processes (Yoneda et al. 2017).

Yoneda et al. examined whether orally administered theobromine functions as a central phosphodiesterase (PDE) inhibitor and modulates the cAMP/CREB/BDNF signaling cascade, as well as learning performance in mice. Their findings showed that levels of p-VASP, p-CREB, and BDNF in the brain were elevated in the theobromine-treated group compared with control animals. Moreover, theobromine-treated mice demonstrated superior performance in the three-lever task. Collectively, these results indicate that oral theobromine can act as a PDE inhibitor in the brain, enhancing cAMP/CREB/BDNF signaling and improving motor learning in mice (Yoneda et al. 2017).

Theobromine inhibits the activity of poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase 1 (PARP-1), a nuclear enzyme essential for DNA repair and for regulating immune processes, including gene transcription in dendritic cells, macrophages, and lymphocytes. PARP-1 plays a multifaceted role in the immune system by modulating inflammatory responses and influencing both innate and adaptive immunity. Theobromine's inhibition of PARP-1 is thought to contribute to its immunomodulatory properties (Zhang et al. 2024).

Theobromine has been shown to possess neuroprotective effects, preventing neuronal damage, enhancing motor memory and cognitive function. Due to its low side-effect profile and minimal toxicity at appropriate doses, theobromine and its derivatives are considered promising

agents for the prevention of neurological disorders, offering potential applications in medicine. However, current research is still limited, primarily based on animal studies, with relatively few clinical investigations.

The potential cognitive benefits of theobromine in humans were first suggested by Gao et al., who reported a positive association between daily dietary theobromine intake and cognitive performance in a representative U.S. population (Gao et al. 2022). Zhao et al. further investigated this relationship in elderly Americans, indicating that theobromine intake may help prevent cognitive decline in older men (Zhao et al. 2023). Conversely, Xinyu Li et al. observed a positive correlation between dietary theobromine and depression, suggesting potential adverse effects, although evidence remains limited (Li et al. 2022).

Bhat et al. demonstrated the neuroprotective effects of theobromine in a rat model of transient global cerebral ischemia/reperfusion (tGCI/R). Theobromine reduced levels of TBARS, a marker of lipid peroxidation, while increasing glutathione content, highlighting its role in preserving glutamatergic and GABAergic neurotransmission following tGCI injury (Bhat et al. 2021). Transient global cerebral ischemia, characterized by a brief reduction in cerebral blood flow, leads to neuronal dysfunction and is considered a precursor to stroke (Wen et al. 2021). Neuroprotection encompasses interventions that protect, restore, or regenerate neural tissue by disrupting the ischemia-induced cascade of events (Haupt et al. 2023). Theobromine has been shown to mitigate cerebral ischemia and hypoxia, prevent central nervous system damage, and support neuronal repair and regeneration, indicating its potential utility in the prevention of stroke and cerebral hemorrhage.

The neuroprotective and preventive effects of theobromine have been demonstrated across multiple experimental models. Hypercholesterolemia is known to increase blood-brain barrier permeability (Acharya et al. 2013). In a study by Mendiola-Precoma et al., cognitive and memory impairments were induced in six-month-old rats via a high-cholesterol diet, and administration of 30 mg of theobromine mitigated these deficits, improving both memory and cognitive performance (Mendiola-Precoma et al. 2016). Similarly, Bhat and Kumar, using a chronic cerebral hypoperfusion rat model, reported that theobromine reduced latency to fall in the rotarod test, increased latency in the Elevated Plus Maze, and enhanced recognition memory in the Novel Object Recognition Test (Bhat et al. 2022). Collectively, these studies indicate that theobromine can improve motor and cognitive functions, underscoring its potential role in memory enhancement.

Theobromine has been shown to enhance memory-related processes in the hippocampus. It is proposed that theobromine modulates hippocampal neuron function and protects them from damage by regulating adenosine receptors. Valada et al. performed electrophysiological recordings in mouse hippocampal synapses, demonstrating that theobromine increases synaptic transmission while reducing the magnitude of long-term

potentiation (LTP). These effects were reversed by adenosine deaminase, and antagonists of A1R and A2AR receptors blocked theobromine's facilitation of synaptic transmission and its LTP attenuation, respectively. These results suggest that theobromine modulates information flow through adenosine receptor antagonism, thereby normalizing synaptic plasticity and potentially providing neuroprotective benefits in dementia-related conditions (Valada et al. 2022).

Monoamine oxidase (MAO) – isoforms and function

Monoamine oxidase (MAO) is an enzyme responsible for the oxidative deamination of biogenic amines and is located on the outer mitochondrial membrane. It plays a key role in metabolizing neuroactive monoamines in the brain, including dopamine, norepinephrine, serotonin, and melatonin. MAO exists in two isoforms, MAO-A and MAO-B, which differ in substrate specificity and cellular localization (Booysen et al. 2011; Cho et al. 2021).

The catabolism of dopamine (DA) into inactive metabolites is mediated by catechol-O-methyltransferase (COMT) as well as monoamine oxidase A (MAO-A) and monoamine oxidase B (MAO-B). MAO catalyzes the oxidative deamination of DA, generating 3,4-dihydroxyphenylacetaldehyde (DOPAL) and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). Subsequently, DOPAL is further metabolized by aldehyde dehydrogenase (ADH) to form 3,4-dihydroxyphenylacetic acid (DOPAC). In the presence of ferrous iron (Fe^{2+}), H_2O_2 can participate in Fenton chemistry, leading to the formation of highly reactive free radicals and other reactive oxygen species (ROS). In parallel, COMT converts DA to 3-methoxytyramine, which is subsequently metabolized by MAO to homovanillic acid (HVA) (Xu et al. 2022) (Fig. 3).

Monoamine oxidase isoforms A and B are flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD)–dependent enzymes anchored to the mitochondrial membrane that catalyze the oxidative deamination at the α -carbon of a broad range of amine substrates. Human MAO-A and MAO-B are composed of 529 and 520 amino acids, respectively, with the FAD cofactor covalently attached to a conserved cysteine residue (Cys-406 in MAO-A and Cys-397 in MAO-B). Although encoded by distinct genes, the two enzymes exhibit approximately 70% sequence homology.

X-ray crystallographic analyses have revealed that MAO-A and MAO-B possess highly similar active-site architectures and spatial arrangements, differing in only 6 out of 16 amino acid residues that constitute the catalytic pocket. Despite this high degree of structural conservation, the two isoenzymes display distinct substrate preferences and inhibitor selectivities (Booysen et al. 2011).

MAO-A preferentially metabolizes key monoamine neurotransmitters, including serotonin and norepinephrine, as well as dietary amines such as tyramine, whereas MAO-B primarily catalyzes the oxidation of exogenous amines, notably benzylamine and phenylethylamine. Dopamine serves as a common substrate for both MAO isoforms. MAO-A primarily metabolizes epinephrine, norepinephrine, serotonin, and melatonin and is predominantly found at nigrostriatal dopaminergic axon terminals, whereas MAO-B mainly degrades phenylethylamine and benzylamine and is largely expressed in astrocytes and serotonergic neurons (Cho et al. 2021; Booysen et al. 2011).

Because both MAO-A and MAO-B participate in the catabolism of monoaminergic neurotransmitters, pharmacological inhibition of these enzymes has been widely adopted in the management of several neurological and psychiatric disorders. Inhibition of MAO-A suppresses the central oxidative breakdown of serotonin and underlies the therapeutic use of MAO-A inhibitors

Figure 3. Metabolism of dopamine.

as antidepressant agents. In contrast, MAO-B inhibitors limit the MAO-B-mediated oxidative metabolism of dopamine in the brain and are therefore integral to the treatment of Parkinson's disease (Booysen et al. 2011).

Notably, MAO-B activity and expression increase with advancing age across multiple brain regions, including the basal ganglia, whereas MAO-A activity remains relatively stable. Consequently, in the aging parkinsonian brain, MAO-B is regarded as the predominant isoenzyme responsible for dopamine degradation. By preserving dopamine levels within the basal ganglia, MAO-B inhibitors provide symptomatic improvement in patients with Parkinson's disease. These agents are commonly administered in combination with levodopa, as inhibition of MAO-B enhances levodopa-derived dopamine availability. This combined approach may allow for lower levodopa dosages, thereby reducing the incidence of levodopa-associated adverse effects.

Beyond their symptomatic benefits, monoamine oxidases are also implicated in the neurodegenerative mechanisms of Parkinson's disease. The MAO-catalyzed oxidation of dopamine generates equimolar amounts of hydrogen peroxide, a contributor to oxidative stress, and 3,4-dihydroxyphenylacetaldehyde (DOPAL), a highly reactive metabolite capable of modifying nucleic acids and proteins. By attenuating dopamine metabolism, MAO inhibitors decrease the production of these cytotoxic by-products and are therefore considered potential disease-modifying agents with neuroprotective properties that may slow the progression of Parkinson's disease (Booysen et al. 2011).

A key objective of Parkinson's disease therapy is the preservation of nigrostriatal dopaminergic neurons by counteracting the underlying neurodegenerative processes. Although no treatment has yet been conclusively proven to provide neuroprotection, both clinical and preclinical evidence indicate that MAO-B inhibitors may slow disease progression in early-stage PD. For instance, a seven-year study demonstrated that (R)-deprenyl, administered either as monotherapy or in combination with levodopa, reduced the rate of disease progression compared to placebo-treated patients. Likewise, a one-year trial of rasagiline monotherapy in PD patients suggested potential neuroprotective effects in addition to its symptomatic benefits (Petzer et al. 2009) (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Monoamine oxidase (MAO)-B catalyzed oxidation of dopamine.

The neuroprotective potential of MAO-B inhibitors can be partly attributed to the reduction of toxic metabolic by-products generated during MAO-B-mediated monoamine oxidation. In each catalytic cycle, MAO-B

produces equimolar amounts of an iminium intermediate—subsequently hydrolyzed to the corresponding aldehyde—and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) for every mole of substrate oxidized. If not efficiently neutralized by centrally located aldehyde dehydrogenase (ADH) and glutathione peroxidase, these catabolic products can be neurotoxic. Accumulated H₂O₂ can participate in Fenton reactions with ferrous ions, forming highly reactive hydroxyl radicals that damage proteins, DNA, lipids, carbohydrates, and amino acids. This mechanism is particularly relevant in Parkinson's disease, given the age-related increase in both MAO-B activity and cerebral iron levels. Moreover, glutathione levels, which are essential for H₂O₂ detoxification via glutathione peroxidase, are often reduced in the parkinsonian brain, and ADH expression is diminished in the substantia nigra of PD patients. Such deficiencies may facilitate the accumulation of toxic aldehyde species derived from MAO-B activity. Accordingly, MAO-B inhibitors may provide neuroprotection by limiting the production of both aminyl-derived aldehydes and H₂O₂ in the central nervous system (Petzer et al. 2009).

A second, more conceptual basis for considering MAO-B inhibitors as neuroprotective stems from the involvement of MAO-B in neurodegenerative processes triggered by xenobiotic amines. For example, the parkinsonian pro-toxin MPTP undergoes its initial bioactivation step through MAO-B, ultimately forming 1-methyl-4-phenylpyridinium (MPP⁺), a mitochondrial toxin that selectively damages nigrostriatal dopaminergic neurons in both humans and animal models. MAO-B inhibitors confer protection against MPTP-induced neurotoxicity, primarily by preventing this metabolic activation. The observation that a small exogenous molecule can induce parkinsonism has led to speculation about the existence of endogenous or environmental neurotoxins contributing to the pathogenesis of PD. If such putative neurotoxins require MAO-B-mediated bioactivation, MAO-B inhibitors could theoretically offer protection against idiopathic PD. However, to date, no endogenous or environmental MPTP-like compound has been identified as a confirmed contributor to Parkinson's disease (Latosińska et al. 2014).

Selective inhibitors have been developed to target each isoenzyme: MAO-A inhibitors such as clorgiline and moclobemide, and MAO-B inhibitors including selegiline, rasagiline, safinamide, and KDS2010. These inhibitors are commonly used in the treatment of depression (MAO-A) and Parkinson's disease (MAO-B), respectively (Cho et al. 2021). Dopamine agonists (DAs) and enzyme inhibitors, including catechol-O-methyltransferase (COMT) inhibitors and monoamine oxidase B (MAO-B) inhibitors, are frequently used as adjuncts to levodopa to manage motor complications in Parkinson's disease (PD). COMT inhibitors, such as entacapone and opicapone, prevent peripheral levodopa degradation, whereas MAO-B inhibitors cross the blood-brain barrier, inhibit central MAO activity, and reduce dopamine breakdown in the CNS. MAO-B inhibitors have demonstrated efficacy and safety both in early Parkinson's disease and as adjunctive therapy in advanced

stages. Prolonged MAO-B inhibitor use has been associated with decreased Levodopa requirements and slower clinical progression. Approved MAO-B inhibitors include the irreversible agents selegiline and rasagiline, as well as the reversible inhibitor safinamide (Tan et al. 2022).

Effects of Theobromine on MAO-A and MAO-B

There is limited data regarding the potential effects of theobromine on MAO-A and MAO-B. Wiem Haj Ahmed et al. tested the interaction between several methylxanthines, including theobromine, and primary amine oxidase (PrAO)/ monoamine oxidase (MAO) in human subcutaneous adipose tissue (hScAT). With regards to methylxanthine-induced inhibition of benzylamine oxidation in human adipose tissue, caffeine and theobromine produced a remarkable 50% inhibition of PrAO activity when incubated at 2.5 mM with hScAT. The stronger inhibitory effect observed with caffeine and theobromine suggests that N-methyl substitution of the xanthine nucleus at the 3 and 7 positions is essential for achieving maximal inhibitory activity (Haj Ahmed et al. 2020).

The findings demonstrated that multiple methylxanthines are capable of inhibiting MAO activity in humans. Notably, in contrast to resveratrol and other related stilbenes, theobromine exhibits comparable inhibitory effects on primary amine oxidase (PrAO) and MAO, whereas stilbenes have been shown to preferentially inhibit MAO over PrAO. These observations underscore the need to consider MAO inhibition when evaluating the effects of therapeutic doses of certain methylxanthines and suggest the intriguing potential of the xanthine scaffold as a foundation for the development of novel inhibitors targeting PrAO and MAO enzymes (Haj Ahmed et al. 2020).

Primary amine oxidase (PrAO) has emerged as a promising therapeutic target for the treatment of inflammatory, vascular, and neurodegenerative disorders. PrAO is a copper-dependent transmembrane glycoprotein that catalyzes the following biochemical reaction:

PrAO is composed of a cytoplasmic region, a transmembrane domain, and an extracellular portion. Within the vascular endothelium, the extracellular domain can be proteolytically cleaved, generating a soluble circulating form detectable in plasma. In certain tissues, the membrane-bound form functions as Vascular Adhesion Protein-1 (VAP-1), which plays a key role in leukocyte trafficking across the vascular endothelium at sites of inflammation (Henehan et al. 2018).

Elevated PrAO levels have been documented in multiple pathological conditions, including diabetes, Alzheimer's disease, and inflammatory disorders. Owing to its involvement in a wide range of biological processes, PrAO

has emerged as a significant therapeutic target. Various PrAO inhibitors have been described, and their inhibition has been shown to exert anti-inflammatory effects, as well as beneficial impacts on vascular function, the progression of neurodegenerative diseases, and pulmonary fibrosis, among other pathological conditions (Henehan et al. 2018).

Shanahan et al. 2019 examined whether caffeine-related compounds might contribute to modulation of PrAO activity. Among the five methylxanthines evaluated, only caffeine and theobromine demonstrated pronounced inhibitory activity against PrAO. Notably, the remaining compounds—namely theophylline, paraxanthine, and 7-methylxanthine—exhibited minimal inhibitory effects (Henehan et al. 2018).

The inhibitory profile of theobromine was evaluated using benzylamine as a substrate. The results revealed a non-competitive mode of inhibition, with an estimated K_i value of $276 \pm 44 \mu\text{M}$. This inhibitory pattern resembles that observed for caffeine; however, theobromine exhibited a significantly lower K_i , indicating stronger inhibitory potency. As a natural component of cocoa and a metabolic product of caffeine in humans, theobromine appears to be a more effective inhibitor than caffeine. Additionally, theobromine possesses a longer plasma half-life and exerts weaker central nervous system stimulation, which is associated with a reduced risk of toxic side effects. Its extended half-life may contribute to more sustained biological effects compared to caffeine. Furthermore, it should be noted that theobromine can be generated *in vivo* as a result of caffeine metabolism (Henehan et al. 2018).

A key finding was that, apart from caffeine and theobromine, none of the tested methylxanthines produced meaningful inhibition. For example, 7-methylxanthine, a caffeine metabolite lacking the methyl group at position 3, exhibited minimal inhibitory activity. Likewise, theophylline, which lacks methylation at position 7, was comparatively weak as an inhibitor. These observations clearly indicate that methyl groups at the 3 and 7 positions of the xanthine scaffold are essential for effective inhibition. The absence of significant inhibitory effects among these closely related analogues further suggests that other structural features of the xanthine core play a limited role in enzyme binding.

The lower K_i value observed for theobromine compared with caffeine may be explained by the formation of hydrogen bonds between the nitrogen atom at position 1 and amino acid residues within PrAO. Theobromine displays a noncompetitive inhibition profile, indicating that it does not directly obstruct substrate binding but instead interferes with catalytic turnover. Such a pattern is typically associated with inhibitor binding at a site distinct from the active site, allowing interaction with both the free enzyme and the enzyme-substrate complex. However, the ping-pong catalytic mechanism characteristic of PrAO-mediated amine oxidation permits ligand binding to both oxidized and reduced enzyme forms, which can generate complex kinetic behavior. Consequently, non-

competitive inhibition may arise if methylxanthines associate with the substrate access channel of either redox state of PrAO (Henehan et al. 2018).

Caffeine and its derivatives have attracted considerable scientific interest, primarily because of their potential as dual-target-directed compounds capable of simultaneously inhibiting monoamine oxidase B (MAO-B) and antagonizing adenosine A2A receptors (A2AR) in the brain. Such molecules may provide enhanced symptomatic relief and contribute to slowing the progression of Parkinson's and Alzheimer's diseases by offering protection against ongoing neurodegeneration (Latosińska et al. 2014).

The differences observed in the activity profiles of these compounds, which do not act synergistically, can be explained at the molecular level. All methylxanthines investigated share a common xanthine scaffold composed of two fused heterocyclic rings—a pyrimidinedione and an imidazole ring—while structural variability is limited to the number and position of methyl substitutions. Although these modifications involve only the N(1) and N(7) nitrogen atoms, they impose significant constraints on the overall intermolecular interaction capacity of the molecule.

Theobromine and theophylline exhibit ampholytic behavior due to their ability to accept protons at the N(9) position and donate protons from N(1) in the case of theobromine or from N(7) in the case of theophylline. Proton acceptance at N(9), together with proton migration pathways associated with keto–enol tautomerism, confers weakly acidic properties to these naturally basic compounds, enabling salt formation with both acids and bases. In contrast, caffeine displays a predominantly alkaline character and, due to the absence of tautomerization, is believed to form only weak hydrogen bonds, with N(9) acting as the sole potential hydrogen bond acceptor.

Structure–activity relationship (SAR) studies indicate that substitution at the N(9) position is not critical for biological activity. Instead, methyl groups at the N(1) and N(3) positions are key determinants of MAO-B inhibition, whereas substitution at N(7) enhances both MAO-B inhibitory activity and A2A receptor antagonism (Latosińska et al. 2014).

Limitations

Despite the growing body of experimental and epidemiological data, several important limitations must be considered when interpreting the potential role of methylxanthines, particularly theobromine, in neurodegenerative diseases. Most findings regarding theobromine derive from *in vitro* and animal studies, which may not fully translate to human Parkinson's disease pathophysiology. In contrast to caffeine, there is a marked absence of randomized controlled trials evaluating theobromine in Parkinson's disease, limiting any causal inference in humans. Experimental Parkinson's models (e.g., MPTP, 6-OHDA,

and α -synuclein-based models) capture only specific aspects of the disease and do not fully reflect its complex, multifactorial nature. It remains unclear whether theobromine reaches sufficient brain concentrations through dietary intake to exert meaningful central nervous system effects. Many proposed mechanisms, including phosphodiesterase inhibition and adenosine receptor modulation, have been demonstrated at relatively high concentrations that may not be achievable *in vivo* under normal dietary conditions. Epidemiological associations involving cocoa or chocolate intake are influenced by multiple bioactive compounds, making it difficult to isolate the specific effects of theobromine. There is insufficient data on the relationship between theobromine intake, systemic exposure, and neuroprotective outcomes in humans.

Conclusion

Theobromine, a naturally occurring methylxanthine primarily found in cocoa, exhibits the capacity to inhibit monoamine oxidase (MAO) enzymes, particularly MAO-B, though data on MAO-A inhibition are more limited. Evidence from *in vitro* studies indicates that theobromine, like caffeine, can act as a non-competitive inhibitor of amine oxidases, with key structural features—specifically methyl groups at positions 3 and 7 of the xanthine scaffold—being essential for its inhibitory potency. Compared to caffeine, theobromine demonstrates a lower K_i and a longer plasma half-life, suggesting stronger and more sustained inhibitory effects with lower central nervous system stimulation and reduced risk of adverse effects.

Inhibition of MAO-B by theobromine could reduce the oxidative deamination of dopamine and other monoamines, thereby limiting the formation of potentially neurotoxic by-products such as hydrogen peroxide and reactive aldehydes. This suggests a potential neuroprotective role, particularly relevant in neurodegenerative conditions like Parkinson's disease, where MAO-B activity increases with age and contributes to dopaminergic neuronal loss.

Furthermore, structure–activity relationship analyses indicate that methylation at N(1) and N(3) is critical for MAO-B inhibition, while N(7) methylation enhances both MAO-B inhibitory activity and adenosine A2A receptor antagonism. This highlights the therapeutic potential of theobromine as a dual-target compound, capable of modulating both MAO-B activity and adenosinergic signaling, which may offer symptomatic benefits and slow neurodegenerative processes in disorders such as Parkinson's and Alzheimer's diseases.

In summary, theobromine is a promising natural compound with moderate MAO-B inhibitory activity, low CNS toxicity, and potential neuroprotective effects, supporting further investigation into its role in neurodegeneration and as a scaffold for the development of novel MAO-targeted therapeutics.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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